

A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON SMS Vs WHATSAPP USERS

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Abstract:

Whatsapp is India's largest Fast growing smart mobile software application, touching the lives of two out of three Indians mostly the young growing age people. This application is also becoming considerably quit important in the day-to-days life. It also helps in sharing different information's in different formats like. Jpeg, jpg, mp3, mp4, pdf, audios, videos etc... This growing software is very closely nearing quickly to all the mobile users. The old SMS system, when compared with the Whatsapp is only used to share the text messages and too with limited facilities and found the users quit reducing naturally because of the new versions.

Key Words: SMS, Whatsapp & Users

Introduction:

WhatsApp Messenger is a cross-platform instant messaging application that allows iPhone, BlackBerry, Android, Windows Phone and Nokia smart-phone users to exchange text, image, video and audio messages for free. WhatsApp is especially popular with end users who do not have unlimited text messaging. In addition to basic messaging, WhatsApp provides group chat and location sharing options. Technically speaking, WhatsApp uses a customized version of the open standard Extensible (XMPP). WhatsApp Inc. was founded in 2009 by Brian Acton and Jan Koum, both veterans of Yahoo!

Short Message Service (SMS) is a text messaging service component of phone, Web, or mobile communication systems. It uses standardized communications to allow fixed line or mobile phone devices to exchange short text messages. SMS was the most widely used data application, with an estimated 3.5 billion active users, or about 80% of all mobile phone subscribers at the end of 2010. The term "SMS" is used for both the user activity and all types of short text messaging in many parts of the world. SMS is also employed in direct marketing, known as SMS marketing. As of September 2014, global SMS messaging business is said to be worth over USD 100 billion, and SMS accounts for almost 50 percent of all the revenue generated by mobile messaging.

Review of Literature:

Tulika Bansal, Dr. Dhananjay Joshi (2014) defined in their study titled "A Study of Students Experiences of WhatsApp Mobile Learning" mobile phones are ubiquitous with everyone and there is lot of craze for messenger applications. Researchers has oftenly found their students asking them "Do you use WhatsApp?" or "Are you on we chat?". This tickled their mind and made them think how these mobile applications can help in education, in Global Journal of Human Social science.

Johnson Yeboah & George Dominic Ewur (2014) in their article titled "The Impact of Whatsapp Messenger Usage on Students Performance in Tertiary Institutions in Ghanga" Journal of Education and Practice informed the perceived high level of usage of social networking applications amongst students.

Significance of the Study: The main significance of the study is to know about the respondents' awareness about mobile phone usage especially in traditional text

messages also called as Short Message Service (SMS) and newly developed messenger Whats app.

Scope of the Study: To understand the mobile customer's needs and wants, that include not only whats app but also the SMS, why they find switching from one to another or in certain cases found both the messenger services are used. Thus, from the above information it is clear that the study is needed.

Objectives: The study is carried out with the following objectives

- ✓ To know the socio-economic profile of the respondents
- ✓ To analyse the frequency of users (Whatsapp & SMS).

Source of Data: The data is collected by using primary and secondary data. Primary data is that which is collected by a collected by well structured questionnaire and filled by the 150 respondents. Secondary data is the data which is collected by existing sources. Secondary data were collected from various books, magazines, journals and websites.

Area of Study: Sampling unit may be geographical, such as State, District, Village, etc., the geographical sampling unit under this study is associated with special reference to either College students or their family members of Pollachi Region.

Sampling Design: A Non-probability sampling technique, namely convenience sampling was applied in this research. However, convenience sampling is often used for making pilot studies and used as preliminary before the final sampling design is decided upon.

Frame Work of Analysis: The present study is carried out by using the following techniques to analyse the collected data

- ✓ Simple Percentage Analyse,

Limitations of the Study: The main limitations are as follows:

- ✓ The busy schedule of the respondents was one of the reasons, which happened during data collection.
- ✓ This study uses self evaluation criteria of investigating the user satisfaction, which may be researcher biased.
- ✓ The result of the study confines only to Whatsapp and SMS users in College students of Pollachi Region.
- ✓ Some Mobile users had shown reluctant response to give their opinion.
- ✓ All the limitations of primary data are applicable to this study.

Analysis and Interpretation:

Socio- Economic Profile of the Sample Respondents:

S.No	Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percent	
1.	Area	Rural	81	54
		Semi-Urban	20	13
		Urban	49	33
2.	Age	Below 20 yrs	16	11
		20 – 30 yrs	80	53
		Above 30 yrs	54	36
3.	Gender	Male	63	42
		Female	87	58

4.	Educational Qualification	HSC, S.S.L.C & Below	33	22
		Graduate	42	28
		Post-Graduate	48	32
		Researchers	27	18
5.	Occupation of Parents	Business	30	20
		Professional	15	10
		Agriculture	70	47
		Employed	35	23
6.	Usage	Only SMS	30	20
		SMS&Whatsapp	120	80
		None	00	00
7.	Frequency in usage	Daily	70	47
		Weekly	41	27
		Monthly	39	26

Source: Primary Data

Findings:

Out of 150 Customers using mobile messenger 54 percent of the respondents are situated in rural area. 53 per cent of the respondents belong to the age between 20-30 years. 58 per cent of the respondents are female. 32 per cent of the respondents are post-graduate. 47 per cent of the respondents parent's occupation is Agriculturist. 80 percent of the respondents are using both SMS & Whats app. 47 per cent of the respondents use the messenger services daily.

Reason for the Popularity:

These over-the-top messaging services are popular for several reasons:

- ✓ Free or very low cost
- ✓ More features.
- ✓ Multiple platforms. .
- ✓ No ads.

Suggestions:

- ✓ SMS services are rarely used due to convenience.
- ✓ By research, whats app is considered as the convenient messenger application.
- ✓ It is recommended not to compromise the speed & .accuracy in whats app messenger.
- ✓ Rural respondents are feeling easy to use, due to the importance they feel regarding the usage.

Conclusion:

Once, the mobiles found very difficult to reach every corner of the world but now the trend of mobile application are totally different. With the help of internet, the mobile users are more comfortable in enjoying the task of sharing the information's from one to another. The new reach of mobile messengers i.e. SMS, whatsapp, hike etc are free and does not restricts the message senders with the limitations, by this facilities users found very comfortable in using these applications. Also it can be easily downloaded by online, and could be installed in all latest configured mobiles and their related instruments. By this study the researchers concludes that this have already reached all

the corners of the society and not only the students but also the parents do using this applications.

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